

CHESS SETUP: STEP 6

3rd anniversary of the project!

Welcome to our 6th newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

6th CHESS SETUP meeting in Corby

On the 30th of May of this year, the 6th Consortium Meeting was held in Corby, England. It was the opportunity for every partner to effectively communicate to all the partners about the advances done and next steps of the project. All the works conducted are advancing fastly and the 3 pilots are nearly finished! The meeting ended with a site visit of Corby's pilot, to see in real all the achievements done.

CHESS SETUP pilots

Sant Cugat's sport centre (Spain)

In Sant Cugat's pilot, the construction phase is about to end! Only final details remain.

Since the last general meeting, the major works have concerned the roof reinforcement and panels structure, the hydraulic, electrical and monitoring installation and finally the redesign, manufacture and construction of the thermal energy storage tank (TEST).

The last remaining phase (Start-up and monitoring) has already begun!

Lavola's headquarters (Spain)

Based in Manlleu, Lavola's headquarters have experienced during the last year a significant reduction of energy costs and emissions, thanks to the CHESS SETUP's Solution: the total energy savings nearly reach 50%!

Now the finishing phase of the pilot is about to begin: the system will be on service by the end of the month, thanks to the works carried out in May 2019, mainly the heat pump installation, auxiliary control elements and board implementation.

Corby's dwellings (England)

After the considerable delays previously reported, construction of the Corby pilot re-started in November 2018 and since then, a lot of advances have been made! The Earth Energy Banks has been completed for the first 10 homes, the installation of PVT is nearly complete on some homes too and the Heat Pumps installations are finalised. Some steps remain before finishing the construction of the 26 homes.

Online & Offline

Our Twitter account keeps on getting more visibility

As we enter the final phase of the project, CHESS SETUP (CSU) has never been that popular online. More than 930 tweets have been written since the creation and the page, and we have gained more than 300 followers.

News about the project, articles in relation with the CSU solution and interesting events are shared almost everyday.

Website and LinkedIn page updated

The pilots' sections of the Website is regularly updated as the works continue. All the new documentation is also added to the Website: now you can find newly videos showing the state of the 3 pilots and our 2nd Divulgation Article, published in the Spanish magazine "Energias Renovables".

On a professional side, our LinkedIn page is also more visible with nearly 200 visitors and 30 followers during the last year.

Events and Conferences

CHESS SETUP partners keep up the momentum to represent the project in international events and conferences. Indeed they have participated to more than 15 events in the last 6 months, from conferences to summits and congresses.

Abstracts are also sent to international events organizations to have the opportunity to make people know more about CHESS SETUP's project.

"Energy efficiency measures are to play a central role in reaching net-zero greenhouse emissions by 2050, halving energy consumption compared to 2005, in all relevant sectors, in particular in buildings industry and transport." *Kamila Wacziarg, Energy, Public Affairs Department, Veolia*

In the last months...

ICREN 2019

On April 2019 the ICREN was held in the UNESCO headquarters in Paris. International Conference on Renewable Energy series addresses research and development in renewable energy technologies including energy efficiency. ICREN2019 has included articles and presentation on the latest research on renewable energy technologies, grid interactions, energy efficiency, data analytics, economics and finance, environmental and social impact as well as policy and climate change implications.

CHESS SETUP was there and presented the project to the audience!

CTEC - Energy Transition and the City Congress

On March 6th Barcelona held the CTEC. One of our partners was here to represent CHESS SETUP and collect relevant information in relation with the project.

The CTEC aims at highlighting the role of cities in promoting energy transition and sovereignty.

The CTEC also seeks to generate a debate around the city-energy pairing between all the stakeholders involved: citizens and civil society, the cities' political and technical representatives, the public authorities, academia, the business sector and so on.

Coming soon...

Sustainable Energy Week 2019

The 2019 session of the Sustainable Energy Week is organized between the 17th and the 21st of June 2019. Conferences, award competition, debates and many events will be held around the topic of Sustainable Energy.

All these events cover a lot of different aspects of Sustainable Energies such as Innovative Mobility Solutions, Sustainable Finance or Carbonfuels. The main conference is held in Brussels and gathers a lot of stakeholders from all the European Union.

Click [here](#) for more info.

Support Service for Exploitation of Research Results

In the following weeks we will receive the support of SSER (Support Service for Exploitation of Research Results). The European Union has selected CHESS SETUP's project as an ideal one for completed and ongoing research projects in the field of energy. The purpose of the service is to help CSU to exploit the results of our work in order to achieve the intended mid to long term impacts, specially with the Business Model part of the project. Looking forward to it!

Click [here](#) for more info.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

For more information about the project, you can find us on,

- Our [webpage](#)
- Our Twitter account [@ChessSetup](#)
- Our [LinkedIn](#) page

Comparte via:

<http://www.chess-setup.net>